

Infrared Spectra of Pyrophyllite and Its Mn-, Zn-, Fe- and Cu- Derivatives

ABHIJIT GUPTA*, S. K. DE** and B. SENGUPTA***

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

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The characteristic functional groups arising due to the presence of OH or adsorbed water (between 2.70 μ and 7.20 μ) and due to lattice vibrations of Si-O (between 8.50 μ and 9.50 μ) as well as Al-O (between 9.50 μ and 10.30 μ) of pyrophyllite and its manganese, zinc, iron and copper derivatives in the infrared region have been identified and discussed in terms of nature of bond and structure of the clay samples.

THE infrared curves of some foreign pyrophyllite samples have been studied¹ but a comparative study of the infrared curves of Indian pyrophyllite and its Mn-, Zn-, Fe- and Cu-derivatives as reported in this paper is being attempted for the first time. The quality of Indian pyrophyllite are gradually getting ground in Indian ceramic industries and hence this study will show the importance of association of these trace elements with pyrophyllite in relation to its structural quality.

Experimental

Metal ion (Mn⁺⁺, Zn⁺⁺, Fe⁺⁺⁺ and Cu⁺⁺) derivatives of the mineral were prepared by treating a standard sample of pure Indian pyrophyllite obtained from heavy liquid separation technique with the respective normal metal chloride solutions in the ratio of 1 : 10 and keeping them overnight. The residues were washed, dried and pulverized to fine powder. These samples and the standard pure mineral were taken for infrared studies by the KBr disc method using the Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer model-137. The results of ir spectra are shown in Fig. 1 and are summarized in the Tables 1 and 2. The depth values of absorption curves thus obtained were identified and calculated by base line method.

Discussion

Infrared peaks of the clay samples arising as a result of absorption due to O-H or adsorbed water (2.70 μ to 7.20 μ)² and due to lattice vibrations (8.69 μ to 15.0 μ)³ have only been considered in this paper.

It has been said in general that absorption at 2.70 μ is due to bonded O-H and that at 2.75 μ and onwards are generally due to unbonded O-H. The absorption at 2.71 μ is as a result of coupling of vibrations of two antisymmetrical (out of phase) O-H groups. By comparing the peaks of derivatives of the mineral (B, C, D and E in Fig. 1) with the peaks of the standard mineral pyrophyllite - A in the Figure, we can characterise the following changes :—

1. The peak at 2.70 μ seen in the case of standard pyrophyllite does not change even with the introduction of the four trace elements in the body of this clay.
2. The depth of the sharp peak at 2.70 μ in the standard pyrophyllite varied considerably in Mn- and Cu- followed by Fe- and Zn-pyrophyllite. The absorption at 2.95 μ in pyrophyllite is less conspicuous and broader than others.
3. There are many weak and medium peaks between 3.00 μ and 7.00 μ . The number of these peaks vary with the introduction of metal ions.
4. There are reductions of total number of peaks and strong peaks in the curves of derivatives with respect to pyrophyllite.
5. The perpendicular node of pyrophyllite at 9.50 μ vary at different experimental conditions and the peak values sometimes decrease and sometimes it is absent. There are also absorption peaks at 8.69 μ , 10.41 μ and 10.52 μ .

*Dr. Abhijit Gupta, Chemist Directorate of Geology & Mining, Govt. of U.P., Southern Circle, 63 B-Stanley Road, Allahabad-211 002, U.P.

**Dr. S. K. De, Reader, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, U.P.

***Dr. B. Sengupta, Scientist 'B', Central Board for the Prevention and Control of Water Pollution, Skylark Building, 5th floor, 60-Nehru Place, New Delhi.

Fig. 1. A-IR spectra of pyrophyllite
 B-IR spectra of Mn-pyrophyllite
 C-IR spectra of Zn-pyrophyllite
 D-IR spectra of Fe-pyrophyllite
 E-IR spectra of Cu-pyrophyllite

6. There are also reduction of total number of peaks and sometimes they are absent in the region between 12.00μ to 14.00μ . There is also shift of absorption peak at 12.55μ to 12.20μ in the case of Mn- and Zn-pyrophyllite.

Thus the above characteristic changes observed after comparing the peaks of pyrophyllite with its peaks of derivatives may be explained one by one as follows :—

1. The absorption at 2.70μ is due to bonded O-H and at 2.75μ and onwards are as a result of unbonded O-H² and the peak at 2.70μ does not change materially with the introduction of four metal ions. They are, therefore, arising due to two adjacent bonded O-H groups under the coupling condition³.

2. The increase in depth of the peak at 2.70μ in the case of Mn-, Cu-, Fe- and Zn-pyrophyllites is an indication of greater development of this type of O H ions probably as a result of hydrations of the exchangeable metal ions, the measure depending upon the type of metal ions involved. The absorption at 2.95μ is as a result of adsorbed water because it decreased considerably with the heating of the mineral to 200° . In case of Mn-, Fe- and Cu-pyrophyllite the shift of absorption peak at lower value to 2.90μ

indicate that the bonds of the concerned groups have weakened with reaction of these metal ions. There is further weakening of this value to 2.85μ in case of Zn- pyrophyllite indicating weakening of the adsorbed O-H bond.

3. The weak and medium peaks in the infrared region between 3.00μ and 7.00μ may be said to be due to adsorbed water, the number and measure of the peaks depending upon the reaction of the pyrophyllite samples with the different hydrated trace element ions.

4. The absorption peaks between 8.65μ and 15.0μ due to lattice vibrations vary. As for pyrophyllite it is nine, for Fe-pyrophyllite it is eight and in case of Mn-, Zn- and Cu-pyrophyllite it is seven. It is an indication of gradual breakage of the structure of pyrophyllite with the introduction of these metal ions. Similarly the reduction of a strong number of peaks in case of Mn- and Fe-pyrophyllite (four), Zn-pyrophyllite (three) and Cu-pyrophyllite (two) are indication of very great effect on the structure of pyrophyllite with the reaction of these metal ions.

5. The perpendicular node of pyrophyllite is at $9.50 \mu^3$. This node development can only be seen with the reaction of pyrophyllite in presence of manganese.

TABLE I—INFRA RED ABSORPTION PEAK VALUES OF PYROPHYLLITE AND ITS MN-, ZN-, FE- AND CU-DERIVATIVE

Clay Mineral	Wavelength (μ)														SMW	T
	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0	9.0	10.0	11.0	12.0	13.0	14.0	15.0		
Pyro- phyl- lite	2.70		4.20	5.00	6.15		8.90	9.25	10.50	11.65	12.25	13.50	14.10		4 9 3	16
	M (1.74)		W (1.02)	W (1.02)	M (1.06)		S (1.16)	S (6.80)	S (5.16)	M (1.43)	M (1.43)	M (1.04)	M (1.01)			
	2.95 M (1.22)		5.25 W	5.25 M (1.05)	6.80 M (1.09)			9.80 S (11.33)		11.90 M (1.78)						
Mn- pyro- phyl- lite	2.27		4.20	5.00	6.65	7.25	8.80	9.50	10.50	11.60	12.20	13.50			4 7 3	14
	M (2.54)		W (1.03)	W (1.04)	M (1.13)	M (1.10)	S (7.87)	S (12.4)	S (8.71)	M (1.81)	M (1.68)	M (1.05)				
	2.90 M (1.45)			5.30 W (1.10)						11.85 S ¹ (2.60)						
Zn- pyro- phyl- lite	2.70			5.00	6.10	7.85		9.20	10.50	11.65	12.20				3 7 3	13
	M (1.76)			W (1.02)	W (1.05)	M (1.27)		S (9.62)	S (6.25)	M (1.32)	M (1.28)					
	2.85 M (1.34)			5.25 W (1.06)				9.70 S (10.85)		11.90 M (1.57)	12.65 M (1.06)					
Fe- pyro- phyl- lite	2.70	3.50		5.25		7.20	8.90	9.25	10.50	11.65	12.25	13.50			4 7 3	14
	M (2.18)	W (1.01)		W (1.06)		M (1.18)	S (5.38)	S (7.00)	S (5.00)	M (1.48)	M (1.48)	M (1.02)				
	2.90 W (1.10)			5.95 M (1.02)				9.00 S (8.75)		11.90 M (1.84)						
Cu- pyro- phyl- lite	2.70	3.50		5.25	6.10	7.20	8.90	9.25	10.50	11.65	12.25				2 8 5	15
	M (2.54)	W (1.02)		W (1.02)	W (1.02)	W (1.02)	S (1.12)	S (2.28)	M (4.21)	M (2.22)	M (1.17)					
	2.90 M (1.45)			6.80 W (1.03)	7.65 M (1.06)			9.55 S (4.15)		11.90 M (1.29)						

N. B. (1) S = Strong (Transmittance 25%), M=Medium (Transmittance 25-75%) and W=Weak (Transmittance above 75%).

(2) T=Total number of peaks, figures in parentheses indicate depths of infrared peaks (I₀/I).

TABLE 2—STRONG ABSORPTION PEAK VALUES IN IR-CURVES OF PYROPHYLLITE AND ITS Mn-, Zn-, Fe- AND Cu- DERIVATIVES

Clay Mineral	Wavelength(μ)			
	8.00	9.00	10.00	11.00
Pyrophyllite	8.90 (1.16)	9.25 (6.80) 9.80 (11.23)	10.50 (5.16)	—
Mn-Pyrophyllite	8.80 (7.87)	9.50 (12.4)	10.50 (8.71)	11.85 (2.60)
Zn-Pyrophyllite	—	9.20 (9.61) 9.70 (10.85)	10.50 (6.25)	—
Fe-Pyrophyllite	8.90 (5.38)	9.25 (7.00) 9.00 (8.75)	10.50 (5.00)	—
Cu-Pyrophyllite	—	9.25 (2.28) 9.55 (4.15)	—	—

N. B. Figures in parentheses denote the depths of the Infrared Peaks (Io/I).

The position of this node may be seen to vary in the other cases indicating the variation of the physical state of pyrophyllite under the defined experimental conditions. It is stated that as the crystal size reduces this band shifts to lower wavelengths in the spectra. The two strong in-plane vibrations are said to lie between 9.64 μ and 9.82 μ , thus the value 9.80 μ for Zn-pyrophyllite can be said to form under the group of peaks that arise as a result of in-plane vibration. This value appears to be absent in the case of Mn-pyrophyllite and the 9.00 μ peak value for Fe-pyrophyllite appears to be the third in-plane node. The peak value 9.55 μ seen from Cu-pyrophyllite may be a number of the first two in-plane nodes, the lower value being due to diminution in the degree of order of the structure. The absorption peak value between 8.69 μ and 10.41 μ are said to be due to Si-O stretching vibration, and the value at about 10.52 μ particularly for pyrophyllite is located to be due to O-H bending vibration.

6. The peaks between 12.00 μ and 14.00 μ are conspicuous in case of pyrophyllite but the number of peaks reduces in this region with the introduction of the metal ions into the structure of pyrophyllite. The degradation of structures as evident from Fig. 1 are also supported from the reduction in the number of peaks between 12.0 μ and 14.00 μ while the peak value at 13.50 μ noted for pyrophyllite remains the same for Mn- and Fe-pyrophyllite and disappearing in Zn- and Cu-pyrophyllite. The absorption peak at 12.25 μ noted for pyrophyllite is found to shift to 12.20 μ in the case of Mn- and Zn-pyrophyllite but remains the same in case of Fe- and Cu-pyrophyllite, where the peak values shifted to a lower one it must be ascribed due to the development of a weaker bond of the concerned functional groups. The functional groups with respect to wavelengths may be ascribed after Stubican⁴ as follows :—

Wavelength	Functional Groups
About 11.0 μ	H-O . . Al Si-O-Al
About 12.0 μ	H-O . . Fe Si-O-Al
About 13.0 μ	H-O . . Fe Si-O-Al
About 14.0 μ	H-O . . Fe Si-O-Al

It is obvious that where the infrared peak values decreased the weakening of the bond of the members of the aforesaid functional groups within the structure of pyrophyllite may be conjectured.

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